

Ways to Overcome Stress and Depression in Line with Buddhism

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Abstract

This paper explores the ways how to overcome stress and depression in Buddhism which are distinct in *PiṭakaSutta*. Everyday all of us face with stress and depression because authorities give order and pressure to do the work and one time. *Dukkha*, derived from Buddha's Four Noble Truths, appears on the surface similar to psychological stress. Traditional approaches to coping with occupational stress found that problem solving was the most effective strategy. Part of the reason Buddhist instructions and teachings are so relaxing for people is because many of them are applicable to our daily life, no matter what our take on religion is. This paper attempts to describe the ways how to reduce the stress and depression.

Keyword: *stress, depression, Buddhism, dukkha, community, solving*

The Objective

The objects of this paper to increase people's knowledge of the nature of our mind in our ordinary life, to highlight the fact of that morality is the soil in which development and understanding grow, and learning every aspect of the Buddhist Teaching absolutely and thoroughly leads to the True *Dhamma* to reach large numbers of people who otherwise may never have heard of it and to get opportunities to meet one of its most genuinely humble, compassionate and dedicated exemplars.

1.1 Etymology and historical usage of Stress and depression

The term "stress" had none of its contemporary connotations before the 1920s. It is a form of the Middle English *destresse*, derived via Old French from the Latin *stringere*, "to draw tight." In the 1920s and '30s, biological and psychological circles occasionally used the term to refer to a mental strain or to a harmful environmental agent that could cause illness.

The term *depression* itself was derived from the Latin verb *deprimere*, "to press down". From the 14th century, "to depress" meant to subjugate or to bring down in spirits. It was used in 1665 in English author Richard Baker's *Chronicle* to refer to someone having "a great depression of spirit". and by English author Samuel Johnson in a similar sense in 1753. The term also came into use in physiology and economics. An early usage referring to a psychiatric symptom was by French psychiatrist Louis Delasiauve in 1856. by the 1860s it was appearing in medical dictionaries to refer to a physiological and metaphorical lowering of emotional function.

The Rate of Depression over the World

The epidemiology of depression² has been studied across the world. Depression is a major cause of morbidity worldwide, as the epidemiology has shown.³ Lifetime prevalence varies widely, from 3% in Japan to 17% in the US. In most countries the number of people who would suffer from depression during their lives fall within an 8–12% range.⁴ In North America, the probability of having a major depressive episode within any year-long period is 3–5% for males and 8–10% for females.¹

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² "The scope and concerns of public health" (PDF). Oxford University Press: OUP.COM. March 5, 2009. Archived from the original (PDF) on June 4, 2013. Retrieved December 3, 2010.

³ World Health Organization. *The world health report 2001 – Mental Health: New Understanding, New Hope*; 2001 Retrieved 2008-10-19.

⁴ Andrade L, Caraveo-A.. . *Int J Methods Psychiatr Res.* 24 March 2006;12 (1):3–21. doi:10.1002/mpr.138. PMID 12830306.

Population studies have consistently shown major depression to be about twice as common in women as in men, although it is unclear why this is so, and whether factors unaccounted for are contributing to this.²The relative increase in occurrence is related to pubertal development rather than chronological age, reaches adult ratios between the ages of 15 and 18, and appears associated with psychosocial more than hormonal factors.³

People are most likely to suffer their first depressive episode between the ages of 30 and 40, and there is a second, smaller peak of incidence between ages 50 and 60.⁴The risk of major depression is increased with neurological conditions such as stroke, Parkinson' disease, or multiple sclerosis and during the first year after childbirth.⁵The risk of major depression has also been related to environmental stressors faced by population groups such as war combatants or physicians in training.⁶

It is also more common after cardiovascular illnesses, and is related more to a poor outcome than to a better one.⁷ Studies conflict on the prevalence of depression in the elderly, but most data suggest there is a reduction in this age group.⁸ Depressive disorders are most common to observe in urban than in rural population and the prevalence is in groups with stronger socioeconomic factors i.e. homelessness.⁹

Kessler RC, Berglund P, Demler O. The epidemiology of major depressive disorder: Results from the National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R). *JAMA*. 2003; 289 (203):3095–105. doi:10.1001/jama.289.23.3095. PMID 12813115

¹ Kessler RC, Berglund P, Demler O, Jin R, Merikangas KR, Walters EE. Lifetime prevalence and age-of-onset distributions of DSM-IV disorders in the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 2005;62(6):593–602. doi:10.1001/archpsyc.62.6.593. PMID 15939837.

Murphy JM, Laird NM, Monson RR, Sobol AM, Leighton AH. A 40-year perspective on the prevalence of depression: The Stirling County Study. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 2000;57(3):209–15. doi:10.1001/archpsyc.57.3.209. PMID 10711905.

² Gender differences in unipolar depression: An update of epidemiological findings and possible explanations. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*. 2003;108(3):163–74. doi:10.1034/j.1600-0447.2003.00204.x. PMID 12890270

³ Eaton WW, Anthony JC, Gallo J. Natural history of diagnostic interview schedule/DSM-IV major depression. The Baltimore Epidemiologic Catchment Area follow-up. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 1997;54(11):993–99.

⁴ Rickards H. Depression in neurological disorders: Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, and stroke. *Journal of Neurology Neurosurgery and Psychiatry*. 2005;76:i48–i52. doi:10.1136/jnnp.2004.060426. PMID 15718222. PMC 1765679.

⁵ Rotenstein, Lisa S.; Ramos, Marco A.; Torre, Matthew; Segal, J. Bradley; Peluso, Michael J.; Guille, Constance; Sen, Srijan; Mata, Douglas A. (2016-12-06). "Prevalence of Depression, Depressive Symptoms, and Suicidal Ideation Among Medical Students: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis". *JAMA*. **316** (21): 2214–2236. doi:10.1001/jama.2016.17324. ISSN 1538-3598. PMID 27923088.

⁶ Douglas A. Mata; Marco A. Ramos, Narinder Bansal, Rida Khan, Constance Guille, Emanuele Di Angelantonio & Srijan Sen (2015). "Prevalence of Depression and Depressive Symptoms Among Resident Physicians: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis". *JAMA*. **314** (22): 2373–2383. doi:10.1001/jama.2015.15845. PMC 4866499. PMID 26647259.

Alboni P, Favaron E, Paparella N, Sciammarella M, Pedaci M. Is there an association between depression and cardiovascular mortality or sudden death?. *Journal of cardiovascular medicine (Hagerstown, Md.)*. 2008;9(4):356–62. doi:10.2459/JCM.0b013e3282785240. PMID 18334889

⁷ Strik JJ, Honig A, Maes M. Depression and myocardial infarction: relationship between heart and mind. *Progress in neuro-psychopharmacology & biological psychiatry*. 2001;25(4):879–92. doi:10.1016/S0278-5846(01)00150-6. PMID 11383983

Jorm AF. Does old age reduce the risk of anxiety and depression? A review of epidemiological studies across the adult life span. *Psychological Medicine*. 2000;30(1):11–22. doi:10.1017/S0033291799001452. PMID 10722172

⁸ Gelder, M., Mayou, R. and Geddes, J. 2005. *Psychiatry*. 3rd ed. New York: Oxford. pp105.

⁹ Stephanie A. Riolo; et al. (June 2005). "Prevalence of Depression by Race/Ethnicity: Findings From the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey III". *American Journal of Public Health. U.S. National Library of Medicine*. **95** (6): 998–1000. doi:10.2105/AJPH.2004.047225. PMC 1449298 . PMID 1591482

Data on the relative prevalence of major depression among different ethnic groups have reached no clear consensus. However, the only known study to have covered dysthymia specifically found it to be more common in African and Mexican Americans than in European Americans.¹

Projections indicate that depression may be the second leading cause of life lost after heart disease by 2020. In 2016, a study found an association of hormonal contraception with depression.²

Depression varies from person to person, but there are some common signs and symptoms. It's important to remember that these symptoms can be part of life's normal lows. But the more symptoms you have, the stronger they are, and the longer they've lasted—the more likely it is that you're dealing with depression.

Etymology and meaning of Dukkha as stress and depression

Dukkha (Pāli; Sanskrit: *duḥkha*; Tibetan: *sdug bsngal*, pr. "duk-ngel") is a vital role of Buddhist concept, commonly translated as "suffering", "pain" or "unsatisfactoriness".³ It refers to the fundamental unsatisfactoriness and painfulness of mundane life, and inspires the Four Noble Truths and nirvana doctrines of Buddhism. The term is also found in scriptures of Hinduism, such as the Upanishads, in discussions of moksha (spiritual liberation).⁴

Dukkha (Pali; Sanskrit *duḥkha*) is a term found in ancient Indian literature, wherein states Monier-Williams, it means anything that is "uneasy, uncomfortable, unpleasant, difficult, causing pain or sadness".⁵ It also refers to a concept in Indian religions about the nature of life that innately includes the "unpleasant", "suffering," "pain," "sorrow", "distress", "grief" or "misery".⁶ The term *Dukkha* does not have a one word English translation, and embodies

¹Lopez, A. D.; Murray, C. C. (1998-11-01). "The global burden of disease, 1990-2020". *Nature Medicine*. **4** (11): 1241–1243. doi:10.1038/3218. ISSN 1078-8956. PMID 9809543

²Wessel Skovlund, Charlotte (September 28, 2016). "Association of Hormonal Contraception With Depression". *JAMA Psychiatry*. **73**: 1154. doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2016.2387. Retrieved October 7, 2016.

³Malcolm Huxter (2016). *Healing the Heart and Mind with Mindfulness: Ancient Path, Present Moment*. Routledge. p. 10. ISBN 978-1-317-50540-2., **Quote:** " dukkha (unsatisfactoriness or suffering) (...) In the Introduction I wrote that dukkha is probably best understood as unsatisfactoriness."

Peter Harvey (2015). Steven M. Emmanuel, ed. *A Companion to Buddhist Philosophy*. John Wiley & Sons. pp. 26–31. ISBN 978-1-119-14466-3.

Carol Anderson (2013). *Pain and Its Ending: The Four Noble Truths in the Theravada Buddhist Canon*. Routledge. pp. 1, 22 with note 4. ISBN 978-1-136-81332-0., **Quote:** "(...) the three characteristics of samsara/sankhara (the realm of rebirth): anicca (impermanence), dukkha (pain) and anatta (no-self)."

⁴ Brihadaranyaka Upanishad 4 April 2014, trans. Patrick Olivelle (1996), p. 66.

Paul Deussen (1980). *Sixty Upanishads of the Veda, Vol. 1. Motilal Banarsidass (Reprinted)*. pp. 482. 485, 497.

⁵Monier-Williams 1899, p. 483.

Thomas William Rhys Davids; William Stede (1921). *Pali-English Dictionary*. Motilal Banarsidass. pp. 324–325..

⁶Monier-Williams 1899, p. 483.

Thomas William Rhys Davids; William Stede (1921). *Pali-English Dictionary*. Motilal Banarsidass. pp. 324–325. ISBN 978-81-208-1144-7.

diverse aspects of unpleasant human experiences.¹ It is opposed to the word *sukha*, meaning "happiness," "comfort" or "ease."²

The word is commonly explained as a derivation from Aryan terminology for the axle hole, referring to an axle hole which is not in the center and leads to a bumpy, uncomfortable ride. According to Winthrop Sargeant,

The ancient Aryans who brought the Sanskrit language to India were a nomadic, horse- and cattle-breeding people who travelled in horse- or ox-drawn vehicles. *Su* and *dus* are prefixes indicating good or bad. The word *kha*, in later Sanskrit meaning "sky," "ether," or "space," was originally the word for "hole," particularly an axle hole of one of the Aryan's vehicles. Thus *sukha* meant, originally, "having a good axle hole," while *dukkha* meant "having a poor axle hole," leading to discomfort.³

Joseph Goldstein, American vipassana teacher and writer, explains the etymology as follows:

The word *dukkha* is made up of the prefix *du* and the root *kha*. *Du* means "bad" or "difficult." *Kha* means "empty." "Empty," here, refers to several things—some specific, others more general. One of the specific meanings refers to the empty axle hole of a wheel. If the axle fits badly into the center hole, we get a very bumpy ride. This is a good analogy for our ride through *samsāra*.⁴

However, according to Monier Monier-Williams, the actual roots of the Pali term *dukkha* appear to be Sanskrit(*dus*-, "bad") + (*stha*, "to stand").⁵ Regular phonological changes in the development of Sanskrit into the various Prakrits led to a shift from *dus-sthā* to *duḥkha* to *dukkha*.

Contemporary translators of Buddhist texts use a variety of English words to convey the aspects of *dukkha*. Early Western translators of Buddhist texts (before the 1970s) typically translated the Pali term *dukkha* as "suffering." Later translators have emphasized that "suffering" is too limited a translation for the term *dukkha*, and have preferred to either leave the term untranslated or to clarify that translation with terms such as anxiety, distress, frustration, unease, unsatisfactoriness, etc.⁶ Many contemporary teachers, scholars, and translators have used the term "unsatisfactoriness" to emphasize the subtlest aspects of *dukkha*.⁷ Many translators prefer to leave the term untranslated.¹

¹ Peter Harvey (2015). Steven M. Emmanuel, ed. *A Companion to Buddhist Philosophy*. John Wiley & Sons. pp. 26–31. ISBN 978-1-119-14466-3.

Thomas William Rhys Davids; William Stede (1921). *Pali-English Dictionary*. Motilal Banarsidass. pp. 324–325. ISBN 978-81-208-1144-7.

² Walpola Rahula 2007, Kindle Locations 542-550.

³ Sargeant 2009, p. 303.

⁴ Goldstein 2013, p. 289.

⁵ Monier-Williams 1899, p. 483, entry note: "according to grammarians properly written *dush-kha* and said to be from *dus* and *kha* [cf. *su-khā*]; but more probably a Prākṛitized form for *duḥ-stha*, *q.v.*"

⁶ Walpola Rahula 2007, Kindle locations 524-528.

Prebish 1993. P-77.

Keown 2003.p-92.

⁷ Dalai Lama 1998, p. 38.

Gethin 1998, p. 61.

Within the Buddhist sutras, *dukkha* is divided in three categories:

- *Dukkha-dukkha*, the *dukkha* of painful experiences. This includes the physical and mental sufferings of birth, aging, illness, dying; distress from what is not desirable.
- *Viparinama-dukkha*, the *dukkha* of the changing nature of all things. This includes frustration of not getting what you want.
- *Sankhara-dukkha*, the *dukkha* of conditioned experience. This includes "a basic unsatisfactoriness pervading all existence, all forms of life, because all forms of life are changing, impermanent and without any inner core or substance."² On this level, the term indicates a lack of satisfaction, a sense that things never measure up to our expectations or standards.

Various *suttas* sum up how life in this "mundane world" is regarded to be *dukkha*, starting with *samsara*, the ongoing process of death and rebirth itself:³

1. Birth is *dukkha*, aging is *dukkha*, illness is *dukkha*, death is *dukkha*;
2. Sorrow, lamentation, pain, grief, & despair are *dukkha*;
3. Association with the unbeloved is *dukkha*; separation from the loved is *dukkha*;
4. Not getting what is wanted is *dukkha*.
5. In conclusion, the five clinging-aggregates are *dukkha*.

Dukkha is one of the [three marks of existence](#), namely *dukkha* ("suffering"), *anatta* (not-self), *anicca* ("impermanence").

Smith & Novak 2009, Kindle location 2769.

Keown 2000, Kindle Locations 932-934.

Bhikkhu Bodhi 2011, p. 6.

¹ Walpola Rahula 2007, Kindle Locations 542-550. (Note1. Contemporary translators have used a variety of English words to translate the term *dukkha*; translators commonly use different words to translate aspects of the term. For example, *dukkha* has been translated as follows in many contexts:

- Suffering (Harvey, Williams, Keown, Anderson, Gombrich, Thich Nhat Hanh, Ajahn Succito, Chogyam Trungpa, Rupert Gethin, Dalai Lama, *et al.*)
- Pain (Harvey, Williams, Keown, Anderson, Huxter, Gombrich, *et al.*)
- Unsatisfactoriness (Dalai Lama, Bhikkhu Bodhi, Rupert Gethin, *et al.*)
- Sorrow, Anguish
- Affliction (Brazier)
- Dissatisfaction (Pema Chodron, Chogyam Trunpa)
- Distress (Walpola Rahula)
- Frustration (Dalai Lama, *Four Noble Truths*, p. 38)
- Misery
- Anxiety (Chogyam Trungpa, *The Truth of Suffering*, pp. 8–10)
- Uneasiness (Chogyam Trungpa)
- Unease (Rupert Gethin) - Unhappiness

³Paul Williams: "All rebirth is due to karma and is impermanent. Short of attaining enlightenment, in each rebirth one is born and dies, to be reborn elsewhere in accordance with the completely impersonal causal nature of one's own karma. The endless cycle of birth, rebirth, and redeath, is *samsara*."

The Buddhist tradition emphasizes the importance of developing insight into the nature of *dukkha*, the conditions that cause it, and how it can be overcome. This process is formulated in the teachings on the Four Noble Truths.

Stress and depression in Buddhist view

Depression is a form of suffering, and also manifestation of a disease or disorder. In other words, depression is a proper subset of suffering and disease, much like pain, suffering, birth, aging, disease, death and rebirth, (What Buddha called "this entire ball of suffering.") are proper subsets of *dukkha*. As previously discussed, depression has many causes and conditions, much like limping has many causes and conditions.

Contemporary translators of Buddhist texts use a variety of English words to convey the different aspects of *dukkha*. Early Western translators of Buddhist texts (prior to the 1970s) typically translated the Pali term *dukkha* as "suffering", a translation which tended to convey the impression that Buddhism was a pessimistic or world-denying philosophy.

Later translators, however, including Walpola Rahula¹ (*What Buddha Taught*, 1974) and nearly all contemporary translators, have emphasized that "suffering" is too limited a translation for the term *dukkha*, and have preferred to either leave the term untranslated or to clarify that translation with terms such as anxiety, stress, frustration, unease, unsatisfactoriness, etc.

Piyadassi Therastates that the word *dukkha* (or Sanskrit *duḥkha*) is one of those Pali terms that cannot be translated adequately into English, by one word, for no English word covers the same ground as *dukkha* in Pali. Suffering, ill, anguish, unsatisfactoriness are some favourite renderings; the words pain, misery, sorrow, conflict, and so forth, are also used. The word *dukkha*, however, includes all that, and more than that.

Contemporary translator Bhikkhu Bodhi states that the Pali word [*dukkha*] is often translated as suffering, but it means something deeper than pain and misery. It refers to a basic unsatisfactoriness running through our lives, the lives of all but the enlightened. Sometimes this unsatisfactoriness erupts into the open as sorrow, grief, disappointment, or despair.

Many contemporary teachers, scholars, and translators have used the term "unsatisfactoriness" to emphasize the subtlest aspects of *dukkha*. Many translators prefer to leave the term untranslated. For example, scholar and translator Walpola Rahula states:

It is true that the Pali word *dukkha* (or Sanskrit *duḥkha*) in ordinary usage means 'suffering', 'pain', 'sorrow' or 'misery', as opposed to the word *sukha* meaning 'happiness', 'comfort' or 'ease'.

But the term *dukkha* as the First Noble Truth, which represents the Buddha's view of life and the world, has a deeper philosophical meaning and connotes enormously wider senses. It is admitted that the term *dukkha* in the First Noble Truth contains, quite obviously, the ordinary meaning of 'suffering', but in addition it also includes deeper ideas such as 'imperfection', 'impermanence', 'emptiness', 'insubstantiality'.

Contemporary translators have used a variety of English words to translate the term *dukkha*; and translators commonly use different words to translate different aspects of the term. For example, *dukkha* has been translated as follows by different translators in different contexts:

Some time ago, Thanissaro Bikkhu's book was read *The Wings to Awakening*, where, if we remember correctly, he translated the Pali word *dukkha* as "stress" rather than the more conventional terms "suffering" or "sorrow" or "dissatisfaction." Anyone know if this is isolated, or if other translators particularly in Mahayana use similar diction? It can be recognized that although the term "stress" is pointedly accurate for many Westerners, it is much too narrow a term to encompass the full scope of

¹What Buddha Taught, 1974, p-98.

dukkha. Maybe his intention was to provide another way of translating it, so as to broaden the meaning for those who read widely, rather than provide a single definitive translation.¹

In ordinary usage, the Pali word *dukkha* (Sanskrit *duḥkha*) means ‘suffering’, ‘pain’, ‘sorrow’ or ‘misery’, as opposed to the word *sukha* meaning ‘happiness’, ‘comfort’ or ‘ease’. Contemporary scholar WinthropSargeant explains the etymological roots of these terms as follows:

The ancient Aryans who brought the **Sanskrit language** to India were a nomadic, horse- and cattle-breeding people who travelled in horse- or ox-drawn vehicles. *Su* and *dus* are prefixes indicating good or bad. The word *kha*, in later Sanskrit meaning "sky," "ether," or "space," was originally the word for "hole," particularly an axle hole of one of the Aryan's vehicles. Thus *sukha* ... meant, originally, "having a good axle hole," while *dukkha* meant "having a poor axle hole," leading to discomfort.²

Signs and symptoms of stress overload

The following table lists some of the common warning signs and symptoms of stress. The more signs and symptoms you notice in yourself, the closer you may be to stress overload.

Stress Warning Signs and Symptoms

Cognitive Symptoms

- Memory problems
- Inability to concentrate
- Poor judgment
- Seeing only the negative
- Anxious or racing thoughts
- Constant worrying

Emotional Symptoms

- Moodiness
- Irritability or short temper
- Agitation, inability to relax
- Feeling overwhelmed
- Sense of loneliness and isolation
- Depression or general unhappiness

Physical Symptoms

Behavioral Symptoms

¹ Dukkha can be translated as follows: Anguish, Anxiety (Chogyam Trungpa, *The Truth of Suffering*, pp. 8–10), Affliction (Brazier), Dissatisfaction (Pema Chodron, Chogyam Trunpa), Discomfort, Discontent, Frustration (Dalai Lama, *Four Noble Truths*, p. 38), Misery, Sorrow, **Stress** (Thanissaro Bhikkhu, Jon Kabat-Zin), Suffering (Thich Nhat Hanh, Ajahn Succito, Chogyam Trungpa, Rupert Gethin, Dalai Lama, *et al.*), Uneasiness (Chogyam Trungpa), Unease (Rupert Gethin), Unhappiness, and Unsatisfactoriness (Dalai Lama, Bhikkhu Bodhi, Rupert Gethin, *et al.*). Bhikkhu Bodhi presents a slightly different list of the eight types of suffering, as follows: birth (*jāti*), aging (*jarā*), disease (*byādhī*), Death (*marāṇa*), sorrow, lamentation, pain, grief and despair, union with the unpleasant, separation from the pleasant, and not getting what we desire.

² **Domanassa cetasika:** [Affection](#), [Anger](#), [Angst](#), [Anguish](#), [Annoyance](#), [Anxiety](#), [Apathy](#), [Arousal](#), [Awe](#), [Boredom](#), [Confidence](#), [Contempt](#), [Contentment](#), [Courage](#), [Curiosity](#), [Depression](#), [Desire](#), [Despair](#), [Disappointment](#), [Disgust](#), [Distrust](#), [Dread](#), [Ecstasy](#), [Embarrassment](#), [Envy](#), [Euphoria](#), [Excitement](#), [Fear](#), [Frustration](#), [Gratitude](#), [Grief](#), [Guilt](#), [Happiness](#), [Hatred](#), [Hope](#), [Horror](#), [Hostility](#), [Hurt](#), [Hysteria](#), [Indifference](#), [Interest](#), [Jealousy](#), [Joy](#), [Loathing](#), [Loneliness](#), [Love](#), [Lust](#), [Outrage](#), [Panic](#), [Passion](#), [Pity](#), [Pleasure](#), [Pride](#), [Rage](#), [Regret](#), [Relief](#), [Remorse](#), [Sadness](#), [Satisfaction](#), [Schadenfreude](#), [Self-confidence](#), [Shame](#), [Shock](#), [Shyness](#), [Sorrow](#), [Suffering](#), [Surprise](#), [Terror](#), [Trust](#), [Wonder](#), [Worry](#), [Zeal](#), and [Zest](#).

- Aches and pains
- Diarrhea or constipation
- Nausea, dizziness
- Chest pain, rapid heartbeat
- Loss of sex drive
- Frequent colds
- Eating more or less
- Sleeping too much or too little
- Isolating yourself from others
- Procrastinating or neglecting responsibilities
- Using alcohol, cigarettes, or drugs to relax
- Nervous habits (e.g. nail biting, pacing)

Eight worldly conditions:

A Buddhist practitioner is encouraged to approach the following eight worldly experiences, conditions, realities in a moderate manner.

Pleasant/Like

1. Pleasures
2. Praise
3. Fame
4. Profit/Gain

Unpleasant/Dislike

5. Pains
6. Blame
7. Shame/Dishonour
8. Losses

How to overcome stress and depression

The following picture shows the process of mind state. The sound from the verbal action can be heard in your ears and mind or brain generates the expecting and tangling images as the experience which you have ever seen, heard, smelt, tasted and felt before like that.

If you like Wut Hmone Shwe Yi, you will be pleased with her image appearing in your sensation. This is not real one which everyone imagines as his satisfactoriness coming out of the different images in his mind. You notice that when you spell Wut Hmone Shwe Yi, if you pronounce Hmone, Wut will disappear in your spelling. According to Buddhism, Wut Home Shwe Yi is only sound which constitutes of four syllables. If you imagine that sound as the image of girl which is a well-known person, you will be happy or unhappy with the image which you like or dislike. At that time, your mind is running from the past to future to and fro. Accordingly, if you have to stay at the present, you will be free from stress and depression. It can be seen in the following example.

How Buddha overcome to Āḷavaka' fury

Meeting with Buddha and ālavaka

Ālavaka *Sutta* records the eight questions asked of the Buddha by Aḷavaka Yakkha and the answers given by the Buddha.¹ It is said that Aḷavaka's parents had learnt the questions and their answers from Kassapa Buddha and had taught them to Aḷavaka in his youth; but he could not remember them and, in order that they might be preserved, he had them written on a gold leaf with red paint, and this he stored away in his palace. When the Buddha answered the questions he found that the answers were exactly the same as those given by Kassapa.²

This sutta can be found both in Sutta Nipāta³ and in the Samyutta Nikāya⁴. The Aḷavaka Sutta is also included in the collection of Parittas.

It is stated that on one occasion the Blessed One was staying at Alavi in the haunt of the Aḷavaka yakkha. Then the Aḷavaka yakkha went to the Blessed One and on arrival said to him: "Get out, contemplative!"

[Saying,] "All right, my friend," the Blessed One went out.

"Come in, contemplative!"

[Saying,] "All right, my friend," the Blessed One went in.

A second time... A third time, the Aḷavaka yakkha said to the Blessed One, "Get out, contemplative!"

[Saying,] "All right, my friend," the Blessed One went out.

"Come in, contemplative!"

[Saying,] "All right, my friend," the Blessed One went in.

Then a fourth time, the Aḷavaka yakkha said to the Blessed One, "Get out, contemplative!"

"I won't go out, my friend. Do what you have to do."

If you were Buddha at that situation, how to solve it? First of all we need to think of that situation, nevertheless, the Aḷavaka ordered Buddha to get out and come in thrice, why the Buddha accepted its orders. This is problematic situation which he meet with the problem how to overcome and which ways how to use it. At that time, the Buddha had not confronted with Aḷavaka yakkha but the Buddha kept his order carried out coming and going in Aḷavaka Palace. Why the Buddha did not refuse his order, the Buddha wanted Aḷavaka to reduce his

¹ SnA.i.228

² SnA.i.231.

³ Sn-(pp.31-3)

⁴ Sn (i.213ff)

anger gradually and the maximum rate of his anger stretched out and delayed his time to review himself. This is the way to overcome anger, stress, depression and other hindrance.

How the Buddha performed when he met with Kisāgotamī

This is an outstanding example of how to eliminate depression and despair (Soka : Pāli). The story is about Kīsa Gotami. Kīsa Gotami was the wife of a wealthy man of Savatthi. Her story is one of the more famous ones in Buddhism.

After losing her only child, Kisa Gotami¹ became desperate and asked if anyone can help her. Her sorrow was so great that many thought she had already lost her mind. An old man told her to meet Buddha. Buddha told her that before he could bring the child back to life, she should find white mustard seeds from a family where no one had died. She desperately went from house to house, but to her disappointment, she could not find a house that had not suffered the death of a family member. Finally the realization struck her that there is no house free from mortality. She returned to the Buddha, who comforted her and preached to her the truth. She was awakened and entered the first stage of Arhatship. Eventually, she became an Arhat.

Buddha solved her Soka (Depression) using his morality technique moderated to her internal heart flamed with lamentation in that Situation. If Buddha refused her demand to bring the child to life, Kisa Gotami would blame the Buddha in public audience because of lacking her mindfulness with her dead son. Were you Buddha in that situation, how you would response. Accordingly, Buddha suggested her to find out Mustard seed and this is another problem to reflect herself with mindfulness. It can be found that another problem can reduce her sorrow because the finding of mustard seed is the first priority to her and bringing her son back to life, only the second one.

Every family had lost a family member. Kisa Gotami² finally came to realise that there way no one in the world who never lost a family member. She now understood that death is inevitable and a natural part of life.

Putting aside her grief, she buried her son in the forest. She then returned to the Buddha and became his follower. This makes her sorrow halve and free from anxiety. It can be mentioned in a the diagram as follows:

¹SN 5.3.

²"Gotami Sutta" (SN 5.3), [Bhikkhuni](#) Kisa Gotami declares:

I've gotten past the killing of [my] sons,

have made that the end

to [my search for] men.

I don't grieve,

I don't weep....

It's everywhere destroyed — delight.

The mass of darkness is shattered.

Having defeated the army of death, free of fermentations I dwell. Thanissaro (1998).

Mind Influence

When it is appeared in your mind whether stress or depression, you can reduced with using this method.

Conclusion

Buddhism provides a very unique perspective on stress, which differs, both in assumptions and emphasis, from the prevailing paradigm on stress and coping in Western psychology. Buddhism offers a more general framework of suffering and stress, and this conceptual framework characterizes the Buddhist view of the human condition. In the West, stress is originally an engineering concept referring to the external pressure exerted on some structure or material. Therefore, psychological stressors typically refer to events external to the individual. In contrast, Buddhism locates the primary source of stress and suffering within individuals – it is the psychological mechanism of craving and aversion and the ignorance about its workings that are responsible for most of our troubles and difficulties in life.

Similarly, Buddhism also provides a much broader and proactive view of coping. Firstly, coping is more than a reaction to a specific stressful situation, but a pathway to be free from all of life’s troubles and sorrows. Secondly, the goal of coping is not stress reduction but the transformation of whatever that is troubling us. Thirdly, effective coping depends on personal transformation, which can be achieved only through mental disciplines and enlightenment. Finally, successful personal transformation not only results in freedom from distress and suffering, but also in attainment of an inner state of serenity and compassion.

In order to practise the Buddhist way of coping, we need to understand the basic tenets known as the Four Noble Truths, which are the original teachings of the Buddha.¹

The Truth of Suffering (*Dukkha*) : Life is full of suffering. In the Buddhist context, “suffering” not only refers to pain and distress caused by adverse circumstances, but more importantly, to spiritual vacuum and disillusionment resulting from the unfulfilling, illusory nature of desires, and to tension, stress and afflictions that stem from emotional attachments to worldly possessions. Thus the relevant implications of the Buddhist teachings on suffering should be found in the overall unhappiness as well as the widespread neuroses and mental troubles that plague modern society.

This inevitably gives rise to the question - can we train the mind? There are many methods to do this. Among these, in the Buddhist tradition, is a special instruction called mind training, which focuses on cultivating concern for others and turning adversity to advantage. It

¹ (Rahula, 1972: chap.2-chap.5; Keown, 1996: chap.4)

is this pattern of thought, transforming problems into happiness that has enabled the people to maintain their dignity and spirit in the face of great difficulties. This advice is found to be great practical benefit in our own life.

Facing with anxiety, it is really helpful to stay in the present moment. Everything else doesn't exist. Kidneys bursting, massive internal bleeding, rushing to the hospital, death, fear, crying, pain – all that stuff only exists in your mind whenever it doesn't exist in the present moment.

That is, it is a fiction that you've created. That fiction is causing you stress. The present moment itself is perfectly peaceful and everything is fine. The fact that mind and body are so interconnected is good news. It means you can affect the body with the mind.

When applied to stress, this means you can use Buddhist psychological tools and approaches to keep you relaxed and healthy.

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